
THE ANALYSIS OF IMAGE CREATING STYLISTIC DEVICES IN THE SHORT STORY OF SOMERSET MAUGHAM "THE LUNCHEON"

Mokhinur Safarova

Bukhara state Pedagogical Institute, a 3rd year student

Abstract: This article is devoted to the analysis of image creating stylistic devices in the short story of well-known English writer Somerset Maugham "The Luncheon". The famous writer was able to show how skillfully stylistic devices can be used through the story.

Key words: character's motive, stylistic devices, irony, imaginary, epithets, understatement, "a modest luncheon".

Introduction: William Somerset Maugham is one of the best known English writers of the 20th century. He was not only a novelist, but also a one of the most successful dramatist and short-story writers. Realistic portrayal of life, keen character observation, and interesting plots coupled with beautiful, expressive language, simple and lucid style place Somerset Maugham on a level with the greatest English writers of the 20th century. His stories are told in clear, economical style with cynical or resigned undertone. The many short stories and books by W. Somerset Maugham contain a unique writing style. His writing style is simple yet it contains a complex and insightful opinion, and narrative⁴. Thus, epithets, irony, repetition and phraseological units are the most widely spread devices in Somerset Maugham's short stories especially in his work "Luncheon" which is considered to be a delightfully humorous narrative and a slice-of-life story about the author's luncheon date that a woman who supported his art proposed.

Literature review: The "two important critics" Maugham referred to were probably Desmond MacCarthy and Raymond Mortimer, the former particularly praised the short stories, tracing their roots in French naturalism, and the latter reviewed Maugham's books carefully and on the whole favourably in the New Statesman. A rising critic of a younger generation, Cyril Connolly, praised Maugham for his lucidity and called him "the last of the great professional writers", but Connolly's contemporary Edmund Wilson insisted that Maugham was second-rate and "disappointing". Even an admirer such as Evelyn Waugh felt that Maugham's disciplined writing with its "brilliant technical dexterity" was not without disadvantages: "He is never boring or clumsy, he never gives a false impression; he is never shocking; but this very diplomatic polish makes impossible for him any of

⁴ <https://www.scribd.com/doc/245644433/FIGURATIVE-USE-OF-WORDS-IN-W-S-MAUGHAM-S-SHORT-STORIES>

those sudden transcendent flashes of passion and beauty which less competent novelists occasionally attain.”

Maugham himself, although he never used the terms "second rate" or "mediocre" about his work was modest about his status. He said that lacking any great powers of imagination he wrote about what he saw, and that although he could see more than most people could, "the greatest writers can see through a brick wall – my vision is not so penetrating".

Critics have focused on what is traditional in Maugham’s writing: his handling of plot, surprise and suspense, his depiction of an exceptionally international, socially wide range of characters.⁵

Analysis: The main emphasis in this article is given to the analysis of remarkable usage of stylistic devices such as irony, epithets, hyperbole, parenthesis, antithesis, to name but a few. Because closer acknowledgement with the figurative language in English literature and, namely, in W.Somerset Maugham’s short stories will help us in better understanding the more complicated linguistic, stylistic and pragmatic problems.

The attitude of the novelist to his character is more to be cynically sarcastic. He likes to play with contrasts and contradictions. His images are disclosed in sarcastic way. The subject-matter of the text is the problem of humiliation and inability to refuse from something harmful. The theme is expressed verbally: "...I was too young to have learned to say "no" to a woman".⁶

The title of the text "The Luncheon" is rather ironical. If we consult a dictionary, we can find out that the word "luncheon" means a "light snack", but as we can see from the narration here a light snack turns to be an abundant and expensive meal.

The text represents the first person narration. The author with narrator’s words introduces us a description of situation which is a flash-back to the case which happened 20 years ago and we can see that this flash back becomes an important detail "Did I remember?"

The message of the text is that people should not let fling oneself at their head. To tell the truth, narrator is very poor person so he can hardly “keep body and soul together”. This thought is expressed explicitly by following examples: "Foyot's is a restaurant at which the French senators eat", "I had eighty francs (gold francs), to last me the rest of the month", "If I cut out coffee for the next two weeks, I could manage well enough", "...the prices were a great deal higher than I had anticipated". By the way the main hero keeps some traditional concepts and he’s educated polite person:

⁵ . https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/W._Somerset_Maugham

⁶ "The Complete Short Stories (Volume III) of W. Somerset Maugham, from Project Gutenberg Canada" <https://gutenberg.ca/ebooks/maughamws-completeshortstories03/maughamws-completeshortstories03-00-h.html>

"I was flattered, and I was too young to have learned to say "no" to a woman". Just by the time you get it that it's not possible to be polite with everyone.

The style of the text is simple. The mood of the text is ironical. Irony is presented here in a stressed form, mainly in scene of restaurant. The atmosphere is not homogeneous. It changes from tense to sarcastic atmosphere. This atmosphere is created through narration, description and dialogues. The dialogue between the narrator and his companion depicts inconsistency of her words with her actions. It is observed through parallel construction: “I never eat anything for luncheon”. – “I never eat more than one thing.”, ” I never eat more than one thing unless caviar”. Obviously it makes the narrator nervous. The primary theme of the story by Maugham is the difference between how things appear and how they are. The speaker wishes that the woman he had a date with was gorgeous and imagined her as a graceful lady. However, on the contrary, he was going out with a rather unattractive woman. The story is laced with humor and irony, which makes it comical in the truest sense. The key themes of Somerset Maugham’s short story “Luncheon” are appearance vs reality, extravagance, manipulation, and vengeance. In ‘Luncheon,’ the speaker hopes from the start that his date (the lady) be a lovely lady. In his head, he sees a beautiful lady. But when he goes to have lunch with her, she surprises him. She is the polar opposite of what he expected. She is a food-obsessed and hungry woman who is unconcerned about the speaker’s lunch expenses. She has a huge appetite and devours even the most expensive delicacies. The verbal irony contained in the phrases she utters to the speaker is the most intriguing part: “I never eat more than one thing.” Her speeches’ sarcasm contributes to the development of the major theme.⁷

Discussion: Any literary discussion will certainly not be true without interpretation of the extracts and passages taken from the book where the essence is revealed. First of all, it is of paramount importance to know the definition of stylistic devices which are utilized through the story.

The author uses:

1) Epithets. An epithet is a literary device that describes a person, place, or object by accompanying or replacing it with a descriptive word or phrase. The word “epithet” comes from the Greek word “epitheton” (neuter of “epithetos”) which translates to “added” or “attributed.”⁸

Examples of epithets in the short story: “little luncheon” and “modest luncheon” (a contradiction with the luxury restaurant Foyot's) - it is used to achieve the ironical effect;

⁷ <https://beamingnotes.com/2021/06/18/the-luncheon-summary-and-analysis/>

⁸ <https://www.studiobinder.com/blog/what-is-an-epithet-definition/>

2) Hyperbole. Hyperbole is a rhetorical and literary technique where an author or speaker intentionally uses exaggeration and overstatement for emphasis and effect. The word hyperbole is derived from the greek word ‘huperbole’ meaning “to throw above.”⁹

Example: “She gave me the impression of having more teeth, white and large and even, than were necessary for any practical purpose” - auther employs this lexical device to stress the hostility of a main heroe;

3) Parenthesis. A *parenthesis* is a tall, curvy punctuation mark used to set off material that isn’t fundamental to the main topic, like an afterthought or an aside (or a funny joke).¹⁰

Example: "(Few men, I may add, learn this until they are too old...)", (gold francs), -by correspondence- are used for explaining of author's ironical and critical attitude;

4) Antithesis. **Antithesis**, (from Greek *antitheton*, “opposition”), a [figure of speech](#) in which irreconcilable opposites or strongly contrasting ideas are placed in sharp [juxtaposition](#) and sustained tension.

Example: "I never eat anything for luncheon", “I never eat more than one thing.”, ” I never eat more than one thing unless caviar” - narrator shows contradictions between woman's behaviour and speech: e.g she repeats "I never eat anything for luncheon", but she eats everything she can.

5) Irony. Linguistic and literary device, in spoken or written form, in which real meaning is concealed or contradicted. That may be the result of the literal, [ostensible](#) meaning of words contradicting their actual meaning (verbal irony) or of a structural incongruity between what is expected and what occurs.¹¹

Example: The story is full of irony. The luncheon date is proposed to the author by a woman whom he ironically thinks is a supporter of his art. But, the lady intends to exploit the narrator by pretending an interest and admiration for his work. She was not feeling any actual interest.

The irony is that the narrator takes her to an expensive restaurant where he’d never dared to go himself. He can never afford it because of his meagre income. “I never eat more than one thing”, “I never eat anything for luncheon”, and “I never drink anything for luncheon” are the very ironical statement made by the lady. Because, she ends up eating a lol of horribly expensive dishes like Salmon, Caviar, Asparagus, Peaches, Exotic Ice-cream etc. These ironies make ‘Luncheon’ a comic story in the true sense.

⁹ <https://byjus.com/english/hyperbole/>

¹⁰ <https://www.britannica.com/art/antithesis>

¹¹ <https://byjus.com/english/irony/>

Conclusion: To summarize the analysis it is obvious that Maugham in this text gave us a brilliant model of the famous English humour. The language of this sample is simple but elegant and refined. Maugham’s style was plain; his insights were rarely profound. Yet in clear, economical prose, he could accurately describe the small details of the everyday world. His short stories tell of odd, unusual and surprising experiences with dramatic, exciting intensity. His favorite method is narration through a third person, or indirect narration, which enables him to pass his remarks without apparent intrusion. Maugham wrote his short story “Luncheon” with outstanding clarity and frankness in ways contemporary readers on the whole found easier to assimilate. True, it can be hard to get past some of the period- and class-based language he falls into.¹²

It should be noted that it is the rare writer who excels at all aspects of the craft. There are masterful stylists who, at bottom, have remarkably little to say. As Maugham has shown, becoming a better writer involves confronting readers’ limitations - identifying those qualities that stubbornly resist all our efforts to improve them. His ironical cynicism combined with a keen wit and power of observation affords him effective means of portraying English reality without shrinking before its seamy side.

References:

1. Holden, Philip. "Maugham, W. Somerset" Archived 17 August 2022 at the Wayback Machine, The Oxford Encyclopedia of British Literature, Oxford University Press, 2006. Retrieved 17 August 2022
2. McCrum, Robert. "The 100 best novels: No 44 – Of Human Bondage by W Somerset Maugham (1915)" Archived 11 August 2022 at the Wayback Machine, The Guardian, 21 July 2014
3. "The Complete Short Stories (Volume III) of W. Somerset Maugham, from Project Gutenberg Canada" <https://gutenberg.ca/ebooks/maughamws-completeshortstories03/maughamws-completeshortstories03-00-h.html>
4. https://smartenglishnotes.com/2021/11/28/the-luncheon-summary-characters-themes-and-irony/?expand_article=1
5. https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/W._Somerset_Maugham
6. <https://studymoose.com/analytical-reading-the-luncheon-by-somerset-maugham-essay>
7. <https://www.scribd.com/doc/245644433/FIGURATIVE-USE-OF-WORDS-IN-W-S-MAUGHAM-S-SHORT-STORIES>
8. <https://www.litbug.com/2022/08/29/the-luncheon-summary-and-analysis/>

¹² <https://www.scribd.com/doc/245644433/FIGURATIVE-USE-OF-WORDS-IN-W-S-MAUGHAM-S-SHORT-STORIES>

9. <https://repo.journalnx.com/index.php/nx/article/download/3656/3526/7093>
10. <https://translate.google.com/translate?hl=ru&sl=en&u=https://studfile.net/preview/6876543/&prev=search&pto=aue>
11. <https://liberalarts.oregonstate.edu/wlf/what-irony>
12. <https://www.britannica.com/art/antithesis>
13. <https://byjus.com/english/hyperbole/>
14. <https://www.britannica.com/art/epithet>
15. <https://beamingnotes.com/2021/06/18/the-luncheon-summary-and-analysis/>